

0.1 Scaling of four phosphate oxygens - 4O

Three scalings of **oxygens** were created:

1. Charges scaled by 0.75. Sigmas not scaled.
2. Sigmas scaled by 0.9. Charges not scaled.
3. Charges scaled by 0.75. Sigmas scaled by 0.9.

Excess charge (0.674) was removed from **phosphate**.